

EUROPEAN DECLARATION OF ANIMAL RIGHTS

Provisional and unofficial translation

PREAMBLE

Considering the fundamental continuity between all forms of life, from the simplest to the most complex, their differentiation being the result of a gradual and progressive evolution;

Recalling that sentience and cognitive abilities give rise to interests which are the very basis of inalienable rights which are already recognised and protected for the benefit of human beings;

Emphasising that rigorous protection of the interests of all living beings, whether human or non-human animals, is necessary, even though they do not possess the same aptitudes, or do not possess them to the same degree;

Considering that the disregard or contempt for the interests of animals and the rights that derive from them have led, on the one hand, to trivialise both the violence and atrocities perpetrated against them and their abusive exploitation, and, on the other hand, to reinforce indifference to the consequences climatic upheavals for them and on their reciprocal relationships with flora;

Considering the moral characteristics of the human species, its place in this world and the responsibility it assumes toward living beings;

Proceeding from the deep conviction that the condition of animals can and must be improved without weakening the protection of the integrity of the human person;

Taking note of the development of animal welfare standards within the European Union, the Council of Europe and the legal systems of the Member States of these international organisations;

Stressing the need to consolidate this European heritage of ideals and values, and to bring to light the existence of a European consensus in favour of a steady increase in the level of animal protection;

The following is hereby proclaimed:

TITLE I – PROHIBITIONS

ACTS OF CRUELTY

ARTICLE 1

No animal may be subjected or exposed to an act of cruelty.

The act of cruelty towards an animal is characterised either by pleasure in causing it to suffer, or by indifference to the extreme intensity of the suffering, pain or anguish inflicted on it.

ARTICLE 2

The following is deemed to be an act of cruelty:

- any deliberate abandonment of a domestic, tame or captive animal;
- any ritual act of slaughter that does not involve prior and reversible sedation;
- any act intended to take the life of an animal which does not cause its instantaneous death;
- any suffering deliberately inflicted on an animal put on show for human entertainment;
- any refusal to research, develop or apply alternative methods to the killing of invasive animals, animals suspected of having contagious diseases or animals used for experimental purposes.

ILL-TREATMENT

ARTICLE 3

No animal wholly or partially deprived of its natural freedom shall be kept in conditions incompatible with the biological and behavioural requirements of its species, in particular as regards hygiene, health, feeding, watering, shelter, exercise and social needs.

Putting and keeping an animal in conditions that are incompatible with the biological and behavioural requirements of its species constitutes mistreatment.

ARTICLE 4

Any animal which humans have chosen as a companion, which has worked for their benefit, which has been used to increase their knowledge or to improve their safety, must have a life expectancy corresponding to its natural longevity under the conditions necessary for its well-being.

ARTICLE 5

The emotional bond established between a human being and an animal must be maintained, in the interest of the animal, under conditions that are compatible with the biological and behavioural requirements of its species.

ANAESTHETISATION

ARTICLE 6

All scientific research and experimentation aimed at or resulting in animals being rendered permanently insensitive is prohibited.

TITLE II – PRESERVATION

ARTICLE 7

No animal may be removed from the natural environment in which it lives for any purpose other than to care for it or to transfer it to a sanctuary, reserve or other place designed to promote its survival and that of the species to which it belongs.

ARTICLE 8

Wild animals must be free to develop their own biological cycles, processes and interactions, both between populations and between individuals within populations.

They must be able to benefit from the ecological connectivity they need for their mobility.

They must be able to live in a balanced natural environment, unpolluted and uncontaminated by human activity.

ARTICLE 9

States have an obligation to prevent the extinction of animal species living in a state of natural freedom.

Compensation in kind must be given priority in the event of damage to a wild species and the resulting loss of biological wealth.

TITLE III – LEGAL STATUS

ARTICLE 10

The legal protection of animals must be not only repressive and administrative, but also civil and constitutional.

Any animal must be represented in court on its own behalf.

ARTICLE 11

The recognition of legal personality, endowed with differentiated rights specific to the animals to which it will be progressively conferred, must be considered a privileged means to achieve the objectives this Declaration affirms.

This *sui generis* legal personality cannot result in obligations or duties being imposed on animals in return for the rights granted to them.

ARTICLE 12

Wild animals living in a state of natural freedom may, as elements of nature or as totemic species, be granted a legal personality with specific rights.

ARTICLE 13

It would be desirable to place the legal protection of animals under the responsibility of an independent administrative authority, called the Animal Rights Ombudsperson.

TITLE IV – EDUCATION

ARTICLE 14

Respect for animals must be instilled in children from the earliest age and feature significantly in all curricula from school to university.

Training modules on animal sensitivity and the specific needs of the species concerned must be included in all school, university and vocational training courses that prepare people to work directly or indirectly with animals.

The Authors

Jacques LEROY

Professor of Private Law and Criminal Sciences. Emeritus Professor at the University Orléans. Honorary Dean the Faculty of Law, Economics and Management at Orléans. Editor-in-chief of the Revue semestrielle de droit animalier.

Jean-Pierre MARGUÉNAUD: Coordinator

Professor of Private Law and Criminal Sciences. Researcher at the University of Montpellier

Séverine NADAUD

Senior lecturer in public law at the University of Limoges. Dean of the Faculty of Law and Economics at Limoges. Deputy Editor-in-Chief of the Revue semestrielle de droit animalier.

Muriel FALAISE

Lecturer in Private Law and Criminal Sciences at the University of Lyon III

Jérôme LEBORNE

Lecturer in Private Law and Criminal Sciences at the University of Toulon

Olivier LE BOT

Professor of Public Law at the University Aix-Marseille. Editor-in-chief of the Revue semestrielle de droit animalier

Fabien MARCHADIER

Professor of Private Law and Criminal Sciences at the University of Poitiers. Deputy editor-in-chief of the Revue semestrielle de droit animalier

François-Xavier ROUX-DEMARE

Senior lecturer in private law and criminal sciences at the University of Brest. Honorary Dean of the Faculty of Law, Economics, Management and AES at Brest University

Claire VIAL

Professor of Public Law at the University of Montpellier. Editor-in-chief of the Revue semestrielle de droit animalier

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